

POWER EFFICIENCY OF HEP APPLICATIONS ON CPU AND GPU

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The Large Hadron Collider (LHC) produces an enormous amount of data from the collisions of protons or heavy ions at very high energies. These collisions generate a vast number of particle interactions, which need to be recorded, processed, and analyzed by the experiments at the LHC. The Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) is a global collaboration of computing resources and services dedicated to supporting the data processing and analysis needs of the experiments at Conseil européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire (CERN). My task was to benchmark these workloads. HEP-benchmark-suite is an application which mimics the usage of WLCG resources for experiment workloads. HEP-benchmark-suite also provides support for measurement of power consumption, load, memory-usage, etc and various other metrics of interest. In this project, I benchmarked various workloads, especially Madgraph on CPU and GPU using the suite and studied energy consumption versus performance on different architectures.

ABSTRACT

To compare the data generated at the [LHC](#) with the standard model, it is necessary to perform [HEP](#) simulations. These simulations can be done in various steps: event-generation, digitization, etc. To understand which architecture is most suitable for certain kinds of workloads, we need to benchmark these workloads for the various experiments at [CERN](#). My assignment involved benchmarking these workloads, especially MadGraph, on both [CPU](#) and [GPU](#). The objective was to determine the relationship between energy consumption and performance on different architectures.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In the recent years, there has been a significant hike in electricity prices. Given the growing demand for computational resources at CERN and the rising electricity prices, it will be beneficial to enhance the power efficiency of the High Energy Physics (HEP) simulations being done at CERN. It is expected that the high luminosity phase of the LHC will demand approximately 10x more computational resources than it demands currently. Hence, it is necessary to optimize the power and time efficiency of these simulations.

HEP simulations comprise of three main stages:

- **Event Generation:** In this stage, the particles produced after the collisions are generated according to the likelihood of their production.
- **Simulation + Digitization:** In this step, interaction of collision product with the detector is simulated which results in electronic signals.
- **Reconstruction:** Here, electronic signals are translated to the particles passing through the detector. This step is done for the simulated data as well as the real data (the data coming from LHC).

The simulated data is then compared with the real data. In this project, I was particularly interested in benchmarking the event generation step since it is relatively easier to vectorize event generation and hence, one can exploit architectures like GPU or even different CPU vectorizations.

We used an event generation application called MadGraph[5] for this project and used HEP-benchmark-suite[2] and HEPscore[3] to benchmark it. We discuss more about these tools in the next section. In the subsequent sections, we discuss how one can run the suite and how the configuration of the suite and HEPscore can be customized to run the containerized MadGraph application. In section 5, we discuss how to customize the configuration to measure metrics of interest, for example: power consumption and load. Lastly, in section 6, the results and analysis has been done for this benchmarking project.

2 APPLICATIONS AND TOOLS USED

In this section we discuss the tools that were used for benchmarking, namely, HEPscore, HEP-benchmark-suite and the MadGraph workload.

A. HEPSCORE

HEPscore is an application which orchestrates the execution of containerized workloads[4]. It can be configured to execute certain benchmark containers on different architectures. It computes the final score based on how time efficient certain benchmarks are on a given server.

For a given configuration, HEPscore is determined by computing the geometric mean of the performance scores achieved on a specific server while executing each workload included in that configuration. The performance scores typically represent the event throughput of the workload process.

To standardize the workload scores, each score is normalized relative to the score of the reference server, which is specified in the configuration settings under the key "reference_machine". For HEPscore23, the reference server is described as "Intel CPU Gold 6326 CPU @ 2.90GHz - 64 cores SMT ON".

After normalization, the scores are averaged using the geometric mean and then re-scaled according to the value indicated in the configuration settings under the key "scaling." This resulting value is the HEPscore score.

HEPscore can be executed independently or using the HEP-benchmark-suite. Running it with the suite provides additional functionalities. More about it is discussed in the next section.

B. HEP-BENCHMARK-SUITE

The suite is a toolkit capable of benchmarking various workloads for the HEP experiments running at CERN. It can be used for the following:

- Imitating the usage of WLCG resources for experiment workloads.
- Allowing running the benchmarks on heterogeneous hardware.
- Collecting hardware metadata and comparing various platforms
- Having prompt feedback and being able to publish results
- Probing resources on a cluster or on a cloud

Figure 1 shows the high level architecture of the suite:

Figure 1: High Level architecture of the hep-benchmark-suite [2]

The suite is capable of running HEPscore (along with the other benchmarks) and it also provides support for additional plugins. I used one such plugin to determine various metrics like: power consumption, load, memory usage, etc.

C. THE MADGRAPH WORKLOAD

MadGraph is an event generator application used in the realm of particle physics. It calculates matrix elements for the Feynman diagrams that one is interested in. The matrix element represents the probability amplitude of the occurrence of the physical process. These matrix elements are then used to calculate the cross sections, which represent the likelihood of the process happening in a collision. Cross sections are essential for predicting how often a particular process will be observed in experiments. After the cross sections are calculated, MadGraph can be used to simulate event generation. It will generate random events based on the calculated probabilities and kinematic constraints. Each event will contain information about the particles produced and their momenta. Researchers can analyze the generated events and compare them with experimental data or theoretical predictions. By comparing the simulated events with the real data, scientists can test the validity of the Standard

Model or look for deviations that might indicate new physics beyond the Standard Model. Note that the reference [6] mentions that *The "sa" benchmark is currently based on a standalone application, using a simplified phase space sampling, which cannot be used in production by the experiments.*

The MadGraph workload [6] can be run on CPU as well as GPU. One can run the stand alone docker container on CPU by executing the following command:

```
docker run -d gitlab-registry.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-workloads/
mg5amc-MadGraph4gpu-2022-bmk:v0.7
```

Listing 1: Running the docker container for MadGraph on CPU

To run it on GPU:

```
docker run --rm --security-opt=label=disable --device nvidia.com/gpu=all
gitlab-registry.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-workloads/mg5amc-MadGraph4gpu
-2022-bmk:v0.7 --extra-args "--gpu"
```

Listing 2: Running the docker container for MadGraph on GPU

In the above command, we are passing `gpu` as an extra argument. One could also run this container with the suite as discussed in the next section.

i. CLI parameters

MadGraph workload supports the following extra arguments:

- `-cpu` : run only the C++ benchmarks on CPU (1 or more copies)
- `-gpu` : run only the CUDA benchmarks on GPU (1 copy)
- `-both` : run both the C++ benchmarks on CPU and the CUDA benchmarks on GPU (1 copy)
- `-eemumu` : $e^+ + e^- \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ (LEP, low computational intensity, high overhead from memory access/copy)
- `-ggtt` : $g g \rightarrow \text{top top}$ (LHC, low computational intensity, high overhead from memory access/copy)
- `-ggttg` : $g g \rightarrow \text{top top } g$ (LHC, higher computational intensity)
- `-ggttgg` : $g g \rightarrow \text{top top } g g$ (LHC, even higher computational intensity)
- `-dbl` : double precision 'd' benchmarks
- `-flt` : single precision 'f' benchmarks
- `-inl0` : benchmarks without C++ aggressive inlining
- `-inl1` : benchmarks with C++ aggressive inlining
- `-p` : '-p<nblks>, <nthrs>, <niter>' for number of threads, blocks and iterations

The default is set to '`-both -ggttgg -dbl -flt -inl0`' (both CPU and GPU, ggttgg only, both d and f, inl0 only).

3 RUNNING THE SUITE

The suite can be executed using the `run_hepscore.sh` script [7] available on the suite repository. To run the script, a machine must have at least 20 GB of free hard disk space and the following prerequisites installed on the system:

- Apptainer/Singularity (version 1.1.6 or higher)
- Python version 3.9 or higher;
- python3-pip;
- git

To run the script, one can use the following command:

```
./run_HEPscore.sh -s SITE
```

The above command executes the workloads in HEPscore. This script is responsible for creating a configuration file, fetching the desired containers, creating a virtual python environment, running HEPscore (or the workloads mentioned in the configuration file) and reporting the results in the desired directory. The report also includes metadata about the server's running conditions. More information about the CLI parameters are given in the script itself. The results can also be published to the WLCG Benchmark Database.

HEPscore can also be executed as a stand-alone instead of being executed through the suite. To do that, one can use the python virtual environment and follow the following steps:

```
python3 -m venv HS23env
source HS23env/bin/activate
pip3 install git+https://gitlab.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-score.git@v1.5
```

Listing 3: Installing hep-score

To run HEPscore, one can execute the following command:

```
hepscore -v PATH_TO_WORKDIR
```

Now that we have seen how to run and install the suite and HEPscore, let's look at how to customize its configuration in the next section.

4 CUSTOMIZING THE CONFIGURATION

A user might be interested in certain workloads only, or might want to pass different parameters while executing the workloads. For that, one can customize the configuration. Let's see how one can customize the suite and the HEPscore configurations and incorporate those in `run_HEPscore.sh`.

A. CUSTOM CONFIGURATION FOR THE SUITE

We used the following configuration for the suite:

```
activemq:
  server: $SERVER
  topic: $TOPIC
  port: $PORT
  key: $CERTIFKEY
```



```

cert: $CERTIFCRT

global:
  benchmarks:
  - hepscore
  mode: $EXECUTOR
  publish: $PUBLISH
  rundir: $RUNDIR
  show: true
  tags:
    site: $SITE
    summer: 2023
  hepscore:
    config: $WORKDIR/$HEPSCORE_CONFIG_FILE
    version: v1.5
    options:
      users: True
      clean: True

```

Listing 4: Configuration file for the benchmark suite

Here, the key `activemq` is used for the publishing purposes and `key` and a `cert` define the path of the key and the certificate for the same. A key and certificate can be issued upon request. Here, the `benchmarks` field can have `hepscore`, `hs06`, `db12`, etc, depending on what we are interested in and `mode` can be `singularity`, `docker`, etc. The `config` under `hepscore` key defines the path to the `hepscore` config file to be used while running `hepscore`. More examples of configuration files can be found in the suite repository.

B. CUSTOM CONFIGURATION FOR HEPSCORE

We used the following configuration file for `HEPscore` to run the `MadGraph` container on CPU:

```

hepscore_benchmark:
  benchmarks:
    mg5amc-MadGraph4gpu-2022-bmk:
      results_file: mg5amc-MadGraph4gpu-2022_summary.json
      ref_scores:
        ggttgg-sa-cpp-d-inl0-best: 1
        ggttgg-sa-cpp-d-inl0-none: 1
        ggttgg-sa-cpp-f-inl0-best: 1
        ggttgg-sa-cpp-f-inl0-none: 1
        ggttgg-sa-cpp-d-inl0-sse4: 1
        ggttgg-sa-cpp-f-inl0-sse4: 1
        ggttgg-sa-cpp-d-inl0-avx2: 1
        ggttgg-sa-cpp-f-inl0-avx2: 1
        ggttgg-sa-cpp-d-inl0-512y: 1
        ggttgg-sa-cpp-f-inl0-512y: 1
        ggttgg-sa-cpp-d-inl0-512z: 1
        ggttgg-sa-cpp-f-inl0-512z: 1
      weight: 1.0
      version: v0.7

```



```

args:
  events: 100
  extra-args: "--cpu"
settings:
  name: MadGraph_Keshvi
  reference_machine: "CPU Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2630 v3 @ 2.40GHz"
  registry: $REGISTRY://gitlab-registry.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/
  hep-workloads$REGISTRY_SUFFIX
  method: geometric_mean
  repetitions: 3
  retries: 1
  scaling: 1
  container_exec: $EXECUTOR

```

Listing 5: Configuration file for HEPscore

Here, we mention that we are only interested in the `mg5amc-MadGraph4gpu-2022-bmk` benchmark and that the results should be stored in `mg5amc-MadGraph4gpu-2022_summary.json`. Here `ref_scores` are the list of sub-scores to be collected from the benchmark container output, and their key denotes the reference scores from the specified `reference_machine`. Each sub-score is divided by its reference score, and the geometric mean is taken from the results to compute a final score for the benchmark container. The version and the weight for the container is specified in `version` and `weight` respectively.

Any arguments can be passed through the `args` keyword. In 5, we pass `events: 100` and `-cpu` as an extra argument to run the MadGraph container with 100 events on the CPU.

Under `settings` keyword, we specify the reference machine as CPU Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2630 v3 @ 2.40GHz. The URLs to run container from can be specified in `registry`. It can be `docker`, `singularity`, etc. The `method` keyword specifies how the score should be calculated. Currently, `geometric_mean` is the only supported method, `repetitions` specify the number of times each benchmark should be executed. If the number is greater than one, the median is taken for the calculation of the score. If, for some reason, the benchmark fails, `retries` specifies how many times it should retry to run it again and `scaling` specifies a multiplicative factor for calculation of the final score.

Note that the `ref_scores` will differ depending on the device and the process that the user is interested in. The HEPscore configuration for running MadGraph on GPU is given in appendix a.. The configuration can be included directly in the bash script for running the `hep-benchmark-suite`. Or one can even use HEPscore to run it:

```
hepscore -f PATH_TO_CONFIG_FILE -v PATH_TO_WORKDIR
```

The configuration for running the containerized application on GPU is given in appendix a. and more about the MadGraph ref-scores is given in appendix b.

C. INCORPORATING THE CHANGES IN THE EXECUTION SCRIPT

Now that we have our configuration files, we can incorporate these in the `run_hepscore.sh` bash script in the `hepscore_install()` function as follows:

```

:
hepscore_install(){
:
:
# HEPSCORE_CONFIG_FILE_CREATION

```



```

    cat > $WORKDIR/$HEPScore_CONFIG_FILE <<EOF
hepscore_benchmark:
:
:
EOF
# SUITE_CONFIG_FILE_CREATION
cat > $WORKDIR/$SUITE_CONFIG_FILE <<EOF2
activemq:
:
:
EOF2
if [ -f $WORKDIR/$HEPScore_CONFIG_FILE ]; then
    cat $WORKDIR/$HEPScore_CONFIG_FILE
fi
}
:

```

Listing 6: Incorporating the custom configuration in `run_hepscore.sh`

One can just run this bash script to run the MadGraph workload with the hep-benchmark-suite.

5 USING THE ENERGY PLUGIN

Along with measuring performance, various other metrics are of importance to us. Studying how the power consumption varies with the load, memory-usage, etc. could give interesting insights and help us use the best possible machines in terms of time and energy efficiency. To be able to do that, we use a plugin supported by the suite [1]. The plugins are designed to run concurrently, and thus they do not interfere with the benchmarking process. They are executed in three phases:

- pre : before the benchmarking starts
- during: during benchmarking
- post: after the benchmarking

A. CONFIGURATION

To use the plugin, one can configure it in the configuration file in the `hepscore_install()` function as follows:

```

:
hepscore:
:
clean: True

plugins:
  CommandExecutor:
    metrics:
    load:

```



```

command: uptime
regex: 'load average: (?P<value>\d+\.\d+),'
unit: ''
interval_mins: 0.1
server-power-consumption:
command: sudo ipmitool dcmi power reading
regex: 'Instantaneous power reading:\s*(?P<value>\d+) Watts'
unit: W
interval_mins: 0.1
gpu-power-consumption:
command: nvidia-smi --query-gpu=power.draw --format=csv,noheader,nounits
regex: '(?P<value>\d+(\.\d+)?)\s*'
unit: W
interval_mins: 0.1
gpu-usage:
command: nvidia-smi --query-gpu=utilization.gpu --format=csv,noheader,nounits
regex: '(?P<value>\d+(\.\d+)?)\s*'
unit: W
interval_mins: 0.1

```

Listing 7: Configuring plugins in the suite

Here, the user can mention the metrics they are interested under the `CommandExecutor` keyword under `plugins`. In the above example, we are interested in measuring load (number of cores used at any given time), server power consumption, gpu power consumption and gpu usage. One should specify the command to measure the metric under the `command` keyword. For example, `ipmitool` was used to access the server power consumption. This requires `sudo` privileges. The relevant information can be accessed through the regular expression `regex`. The keyword `unit` specifies the unit of the measurement and the keyword `interval_mins` specifies the time interval between two consecutive readings. So, here all the readings are taken after 0.5 minutes or 30 seconds. For the workloads which last for hours, one could take a reading after every few minutes or so but for the workloads which are much more faster, taking a reading every few seconds would be an appropriate choice.

Now that, we have discussed the necessary theoretical background and how to run and configure the suite, let's analyze the results in the next section.

6 RESULTS

Figure 2: Measurement Methodology

The MadGraph application was executed on the server comprising of an Intel Platinum 8362 @ 2.80GHz CPU with 64 cores and Nvidia L4 GPU as depicted in figure 2 . The results observed for the power consumption of the server while executing 100 events of the MadGraph application are presented in figure 3.

Here, the aim is not to see which one is faster but to focus on the power consumption of CPU and GPU when each of those are fully loaded, in other words, when the resources of the machine are fully saturated. We can see that the power consumption is significantly higher for the CPU only run. The dotted line in the plot shows the power consumption of the GPU when it is being used. Here, the blue curve is for the execution on CPU whereas the orange one (dotted and solid) is for the execution on GPU, here CPU is used only to offload the work to the GPU. Moreover for the CPU only run, the container does the execution for different CPU vectorizations: no vectorization, sse4, avx2, etc. The first two peaks are for the double precision and the single precision computation without any vectorization. The third and the fourth peaks are for sse4 vectorizations for double precision and the single precision respectively. We see that the single precision takes almost half as much time as the double precision computation. The next six peaks are for the avx2, 512y and 512z vectorizations for the double and the single precisions respectively. One can see that in all the cases, double precision computations take twice as much time as the single precision computations as expected.

Figure 3: Variation of Server Power Consumption with Time

The Intel Platinum core CPU used for our analyses typically operates on ≈ 500 Watts for a dual socket system. One can observe that the increase in CPU load leads to an increase in power consumption as shown in the CPU-only curve and as can be seen in figure 4. As the load increases, a large number of transistors on CPU become active which could have led to the increase in the power consumption. Moreover, increasing the load also leads to the increase in the number of physical cores being used at any given time, therefore, the power consumption increases. One can also see that the CPU load is minimal for the CPU + GPU run since CPU is just being used to offload the work to the GPU. The Nvidia L4 GPU typically operates on ≈ 72 Watts and it increases to ≈ 80 when the GPU is being used.

Figure 4: CPU Utilization

Figure 5 shows that the GPU utilization was 100% for the CPU + GPU run.

Figure 5: GPU Utilization

Figure 6 shows that the single precision computations are approximately twice as time efficient as the double precision calculations while using vectorization on CPU. And since we were using an Nvidia L4 GPU here, which mainly provides support for floating point computations only, the double precision score is really low for the GPU.

Figure 6: HEPScore for different Vectorizations

7 CONCLUSION

In this report, a comprehensive analysis of the power consumption and performance characteristics of the server, comprising of an Intel Platinum 8362 CPU running at 2.80GHz with 64 cores and an Nvidia L4 GPU.

The primary objective was to investigate power consumption under various scenarios, with a particular focus on comparing CPU-only and CPU+GPU execution when the computational resources were fully utilized. I executed 100 events of the MadGraph application to gather data for the analysis.

The results clearly demonstrated a significant difference in power consumption between CPU-only and CPU+GPU execution. When running solely on the CPU, power consumption was notably higher. In contrast, when offloading computation to the GPU while keeping the CPU load minimal, power consumption decreased significantly. This outcome highlights the energy efficiency gained by leveraging GPU acceleration for computationally intensive tasks.

Furthermore, our analysis delved into different CPU vectorization strategies, such as no vectorization, SSE4, and AVX2, among others. As expected, single-precision computations consistently outperformed double-precision calculations across all vectorization strategies, taking approximately half the time.

I also examined the power consumption characteristics of the Intel Platinum core CPU, which typically operates at around 500 Watts in a dual-socket system. It was observed that increasing CPU load led to a corresponding increase in power consumption, as evident in the CPU-only execution curve.

On the GPU side, our Nvidia L4 GPU consumed approximately 72 Watts under normal conditions, which increased to approximately 80 Watts when the GPU was actively engaged.

We aim to integrate the current studies with the upcoming MadGraph container. We also aim to calibrate with the new data for more accurate results. In this report, ref-scores were taken to be 1.0 for simplicity but it should ideally be calculated on the reference machine and then the HEPscores for our server should be calibrated accordingly.

In summary, our analysis concludes that for the given dataset and workload, CPU-only execution results in higher power consumption as compared to the CPU+GPU execution.

A APPENDIX

A. THE HEPSCORE CONFIGURATION FOR RUNNING MADGRAPH ON GPU

We used the following HEPscore configuration to run MadGraph on GPU:

```
hepscore_benchmark:
  benchmarks:
    mg5amc-MadGraph4gpu-2022-bmk:
      results_file: mg5amc-MadGraph4gpu-2022_summary.json
      ref_scores:
        gttg-sa-cuda-d-inl0: 1
        gttg-sa-cuda-f-inl0: 1
      weight: 1.0
      version: v0.7
      args:
        events: 100
        extra-args: "--gpu"
      gpu: TRUE
  settings:
    name: MadGraph_Keshvi
    reference_machine: "CPU Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2630 v3 @ 2.40GHz"
    registry: $REGISTRY://gitlab-registry.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/
    hep-workloads:$REGISTRY_SUFFIX
    method: geometric_mean
    repetitions: 3
    retries: 1
    scaling: 1
    container_exec: $EXECUTOR
```

B. MORE ABOUT MADGRAPH

AS per the reference [6], the following scores for the MadGraph workload are reported (where <process> is eemumu, gttt, gttg or gttg):

- <process>-sa-cuda-d-inl0 : CUDA (GPU), double precision, without inlining
- <process>-sa-cuda-d-inl1 : CUDA (GPU), double precision, with inlining
- <process>-sa-cuda-f-inl0 : CUDA (GPU), single precision, without inlining
- <process>-sa-cuda-f-inl1 : CUDA (GPU), single precision, with inlining
- <process>-sa-cpp-d-inl0-none : C++ (CPU), double precision, without inlining, scalar (no SIMD)
- <process>-sa-cpp-d-inl0-sse4 : C++ (CPU), double precision, without inlining, SSE4
- <process>-sa-cpp-d-inl0-avx2 : C++ (CPU), double precision, without inlining, AVX2
- <process>-sa-cpp-d-inl0-512y : C++ (CPU), double precision, without inlining, AVX512 with 256-bit ymm registers
- <process>-sa-cpp-d-inl0-512z : C++ (CPU), double precision, without inlining, AVX512 with 512-bit ymm registers

- `<process>-sa-cpp-d-inl1-none` : C++ (CPU), double precision, with inlining, scalar (no SIMD)
- `<process>-sa-cpp-d-inl1-sse4` : C++ (CPU), double precision, with inlining, SSE4
- `<process>-sa-cpp-d-inl1-avx2` : C++ (CPU), double precision, with inlining, AVX2
- `<process>-sa-cpp-d-inl1-512y` : C++ (CPU), double precision, with inlining, AVX512 with 256-bit ymm registers
- `<process>-sa-cpp-d-inl1-512z` : C++ (CPU), double precision, with inlining, AVX512 with 512-bit ymm registers
- `<process>-sa-cpp-f-inl0-none` : C++ (CPU), single precision, without inlining, scalar (no SIMD)
- `<process>-sa-cpp-f-inl0-sse4` : C++ (CPU), single precision, without inlining, SSE4
- `<process>-sa-cpp-f-inl0-avx2` : C++ (CPU), single precision, without inlining, AVX2
- `<process>-sa-cpp-f-inl0-512y` : C++ (CPU), single precision, without inlining, AVX512 with 256-bit ymm registers
- `<process>-sa-cpp-f-inl0-512z` : C++ (CPU), single precision, without inlining, AVX512 with 512-bit ymm registers
- `<process>-sa-cpp-f-inl1-none` : C++ (CPU), single precision, with inlining, scalar (no SIMD)
- `<process>-sa-cpp-f-inl1-sse4` : C++ (CPU), single precision, with inlining, SSE4
- `<process>-sa-cpp-f-inl1-avx2` : C++ (CPU), single precision, with inlining, AVX2
- `<process>-sa-cpp-f-inl1-512y` : C++ (CPU), single precision, with inlining, AVX512 with 256-bit ymm registers
- `<process>-sa-cpp-f-inl1-512z` : C++ (CPU), single precision, with inlining, AVX512 with 512-bit ymm registers

REFERENCES

- [1] *Energy plugin*. URL: <https://gitlab.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-benchmark-suite/-/tree/qa/hepbenchmarksuite/plugins>.
- [2] *hep-benchmark-suite*. URL: <https://gitlab.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-benchmark-suite/>.
- [3] *hep-score*. URL: <https://gitlab.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-score>.
- [4] *hep-workloads*. URL: <https://gitlab.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-workloads>.
- [5] *MadGraph*. URL: <http://madgraph.phys.ucl.ac.be/>.
- [6] *Madgraph container*. URL: <https://gitlab.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-workloads/-/tree/master/mg5amc/madgraph4gpu-2022>.
- [7] *run_HEPscore.sh*. URL: https://gitlab.cern.ch/hep-benchmarks/hep-benchmark-suite/-/raw/master/examples/hepscore/run_HEPscore.sh.

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ACRONYMS

CERN Conseil européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire. 1, 2, 4, 5

CLI Command Line Interface. 7

CPU Central Processing Unit. 1, 2, 4, 6, 9, 12–15

GPU Graphics Processing Unit. 1, 2, 4, 6, 9, 12–15, 17

HEP High Energy Physics. 2, 4, 5

LHC Large Hadron Collider. 1, 2, 4

WLCG Worldwide LHC Computing Grid. 1, 5, 7

